

THE STUDY OF THE PROPERTIES OF SULFURIC COMPOUNDS CONTAINING IN OILS, GASES AND GAZACONDENSATES

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Abstract. *The work conducted an analysis of the physicochemical properties of sulfuric compounds containing in oil, gases and gas condensates. Based on the tests, it was found that sulfur is the nearest analogue of oxygen. Therefore, the properties of some organic compounds of sulfur are similar to the properties of oxygen compounds of the same structure.*

Keywords: *oil, gas, gas condensate, elemental sulfur, hydrogen sulfide, mercaptans, sulfides, disulfides, thiophenes, thermal stability.*

Sulfuric compounds are one of the constant components of gas condensates and oils of most deposits. In Uzbekistan, the fundamental study of organic compounds' chemistry in oils and oil products is relevant.

From sulfuric compounds contained in hydrocarbon raw materials, the main danger is the so-called "active" sulfur compounds, such as hydrogen sulfide, mercaptans, carbon cerebral, which reduce the consumer properties of the final products, giving them unpleasant odor, corrosion activity, are poisons for secondary petrochemical processes. Traditionally, the grave cleaning of light hydrocarbon raw materials is reduced to cleaning from hydrogen sulfide with solutions of amines and by mercaptans by water-based solutions [1-2].

This work presents general information about sulfuric compounds present in oil, gas and gas condensate, the main reactions inherent in, as well as examples of the individual composition of sulfuric compounds in oils, gas condensates, passing oil gases and oil products of various deposits of the republic.

Characterization of sulfur compounds contained in oils and oil products.

Currently, there are more than 200 different sulfur compounds found and identified in oils. In oil, sulfur is mainly contained in the form of elemental sulfur, hydrogen sulfide, mercaptans (thiols), sulfides (thiophenes) and disulfides (di thiophenes), cyclic compounds and their homologs (table 1).

Of the sulfuric compounds, the most aggressive are hydrogen sulfide, mercaptans and free sulfur, which are otherwise called "active gray".

A sensitive qualitative breakdown on the presence of active sulfur compounds is the test of the effects of oil products on a copper plate at elevated temperature [3].

Even with a very small content in gasoline of elemental sulfur and hydrogen sulfide (less than 0.0001% MSA), a copper plate, immersed in this gasoline for 3 hours at 50°C, is covered with a black plaque. Mercaptans in these conditions do not have a noticeable effect on the surface of the copper plate.

Table 1.

Sulfuric compounds of raw oil

№	Chemical formula	Name	B _{tem.,} °C	Note
1	S ⁰	Elemental sulfur	134 (T _{пл.})	Active sulfur
2	H ₂ S	Serrene	- 60,7	
3	COS	Carbonyl sulfide	- 47,5	
4	RSH	Mercaptans (Tiols)	6-500	
5	CS ₂	Seroglerod	46,3	
6	R-S-R, Ar-S-R, Ar-S-Ar	Sulfide (thiophenes)	35-600	Residual sulfur
7	 R-S-S-R, Ar-S-S-R	Disulfides (ditioefirs)	109-600	
8		Thiofen	84-600	
9		Sulfoxides		
10		Sulphones		

Modern requirements for the quality of the preparation of oil and gas condensates, for their transportation and storage require the study and systematization of data on the composition and content of sulfuric compounds present in them [4-5]. In terms of the content of sulfur compounds and their composition, oil is very different. The smallest sulfur content was noted in paraffinic oil (0.1 % MS.) [6-7].

In recent years, the volume of production and processing of mercaptan -containing oils and gas condensates steadily increases both in Russia and in other countries of the world, the extraction and processing of heavy carbon oils containing not only ethyl mercaptans, but also a significant amount of hydrogen sulfide, in the region between the Volga and the Urals, are also rapidly increasing. (Tatarstan, Bashkortostan, Samara, Ulyanovsk, Orenburg and Perm regions).

The presence of hydrogen sulfide in marketable oil largely depends on the degree of preliminary separation of oil, as well as on the method of operation of deposits. Therefore, in the literature, one can find conflicting data on the content of hydrogen sulfide in oils and condensates of the same deposits. The content of hydrogen sulfide is an extremely important indicator that figures out many factors associated with the production, transport and processing of gas

condensers and oils. Especially a lot of hydrogen sulfide is contained in some gas condensates. When producing sulfuric and high -sulfuric oils, phenomena are seen when hydrogen sulfide in oils appears after several years of operation of the field. This is due to the factory of oil strata.

The bulk of the oil sulfate compounds has a large molecular mass and a high boiling point. More than half of the sulfuric compounds in oils make up sulfides, the content of thiophene can reach up to 50%, the content of mercaptans in the total mass of sulfuric compounds is generally small.

The following pattern was discovered: the mercaptan sulfur in oils and gas condensates is concentrated mainly in the head fractions.

The content of hydrogen sulfide in hydrogen sulfide oils is more than 0.009% of MSU. The main amount of hydrogen sulfide is removed during the preparation of oil during separation with associated gas. When producing oils containing H₂S, a certain amount of hydrogen sulfide may be contained in reservoir waters. Such waters are dangerous and aggressive, it is unacceptable to drop them into open ponds. A solution of hydrogen sulfide in water shows an acidic reaction and in the air is mutating due to oxidation of hydrogen sulfide to elemental sulfur.

Conclusions.

Based on the tests, it was found that sulfur is the nearest analogue of oxygen. Therefore, the properties of some organic compounds of sulfur are very similar to the properties of oxygen compounds of the same structure. So, Mercaptans are the nearest analogues of alcohols, sulfides are analogues of simple ethers, etc. However, the properties of oxygen - containing and sulfur - containing compounds have significant differences. This is due to two main reasons. Firstly, sulfur atoms are able to contact each other with the formation of chains, the dimensions of which can fluctuate from disulfides to polysulfides. Secondly, the atom of sulfur is much more characteristic than the oxygen atom, to be in a trivalent state, and even four and six-sided states, which are completely stable. This fact is due to the fact that the sulfur atom, in contrast to the oxygen atom, has the ability to use its D-atomic orbits, which are mainly vacant. Since sulfur -heart broaches are less electronegrant than oxygen, such groups as thiol (-SH) or mercaptan (-SR), show much weaker -J effect in comparison with a similar oxygen-containing group in the same molecular environment. Compared to oxygen +M-effect of sulfur is also weaker, despite the fact how much the sulfur atom has a large size.

An important characteristic of oil during their processing is the hydrogen sulfide number of H₂S+RSH in mg, released when 100 g of oil is heated for 1 hour at a given temperature (250–380°C)

$$N_{H_2S} = (C_{H_2S} + C_{RSH}) \cdot 1000$$

The practice of oil refining shows that many sulfur organic compounds have significantly lower thermal power than hydrocarbons. Therefore, when heated in the processing, they undergo a variety of transformations. As a result, it is often that the sulfur organic compounds contained in the products of the direct race, depending on the conditions of rectification, have a composition that is different in quality and quantity, inadequate composition of sulfur organic compounds in the source oil. The works of a number of authors showed that the threshold of oil thermostability, determined by the temperature of the start of the release of hydrogen sulfide or mercaptans, is associated not with the content of the total sulfur in oils, but with the group composition of the sulfur organic compounds contained in them. Oil, which have a low threshold of thermostability, as a rule, differ in a high content of mercaptan sulfur, contain a dissolved hydrogen sulfide, and

sometimes elemental sulfur. Oil, in which sulfur organic compounds are represented mainly by sulfides, have a high threshold of thermostability.

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